
ATTITUDE OF TEACHERS TOWARDS TECHNO-PEDAGOGY

R. Gloria ^{*1}, Dr. A. Edward William Benjamin ^{*2}

^{*1} Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Education, Bharathidasan University,
Thiruchirappalli-24, India

^{*2} Associate Professor, Department of Education, Bharathidasan University (CDE),
Thiruchirappalli-24, India

Abstract:

Teaching jobs are regarded as the noblest of all the professions in the world. The quality of education in any educational institute hinges on the availability of good teachers. “Technology won’t replace teachers. But Teachers who use technology will probably replace Teachers who do not.” It is important to recognize that, the teachers are becoming more knowledgeable of Information and Communication Technology outcomes (ICTs), they continue to have knowledge or skill with which to integrate those technologies into their teaching. As the twenty-first century approaches, the literate citizen is increasingly expected to use computer technology to access and manipulate information. Knowing how to manage electronic information from an ever-widening array of resources and in proliferating formats is essential. The education system was now witnessing a paradigm shift from the traditional chalk-and-board teaching methodology to digitizing the pedagogical approach through technical devices. A transformation would not only increase the capability of the teachers but would also widen the knowledge base of students so as make them competitive in the international arena. The technology orientation needs to improve in order to equip themselves to face the students belong to the digital era and also to face the challenges in the modern classroom.

Keywords: *Techno-Pedagogy; Technology; Teachers; Teaching; Learning; Attitude.*

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1. Introduction

Technology is empowering students in four key ways like democratization of knowledge, participatory learning, authentic learning and multimodal learning. As per the quotes of Ted, “**Technology is a vital part of educating today’s students and it is used whenever possible in the classroom so that improves the overall learning environment.**” Students will also need to get acquainted with technology because they will need to use it in the future. An inspiring teacher not only shows the right path that the students should follow but also prepares the human resource for the further development of the nation.

2. Techno-Pedagogy

Techno-Pedagogy decides whether an Education media product is successful or not. **Pedagogy** refers ‘**Science and Arts of teaching**’ **Techno** derived from Latin word ‘**Texere**’ means ‘**weave or construct**’. Techno-Pedagogy refers to weaving the techniques of teaching into the learning environment itself. Education Technology provides approximate designing learning situations, holding in view the objectives of the teaching and learning bring the best practices/means of instructions which effect on learning.

3. Attitude

An emotional reaction towards a person or thing is usually designated as an, “**Attitude**”. It refers to a **manner of acting feeling, or thinking that shows one’s disposition; opinion or mental set**. It is actually a personal response to an object, developed through experience which can call favorable or unfavorable. Attitude may be towards concrete or abstract things. Attitude may be considered to be one phase of personality. They are closely associated with feelings and emotions. It may be thought of as a response pattern or a tendency to think or act in a particular way under a given set of circumstances. Attitudes are unquestionably an acquired disposition and therefore conditioned by learning or acquisition of experiences. An attitude is a hypothetical construct that represent on individual degree of like or dislike for an item. Attitudes are generally positive or negative views of a person, place, thing, or event – this is often referred as the attitude object. **Teaching Attitude** refers teachers’ beliefs, dispositions and opinions regarding the use of technology in the classroom.

4. Need for Techno-Pedagogy

Teaching holds the most crucial position and helps in the success of any educational system. A teacher is the topmost academic and professional person in the educational pyramid who shapes the learners. Technology is a broad and constantly changing skill-set required of faculty, and selecting the appropriate techno-pedagogical strategies to effectively engage students in the content is a separate skill-set. Media literacy influences student development, and developing a critical analysis of media consumption is an important skill for students. In understanding how technology and media intersect with learning, consider the compatibility between theories of technology and education, and how that relates to the content. There is a need for Teachers as well as the institutional level, to identify and articulate the occupational realities when technology and competencies intersect, while understanding and communicating how technological resources and strategies can engage students and enhance student learning.

5. Attitude of Teachers Towards Techno-Pedagogy

Using technology in education is considered a relatively new pedagogy to integrate technology into curricula. Teachers, who become the main focus during the process of integrating these technologies into the curriculum, face several obstacles when trying to integrate technology into their curricula. Many school districts are pushing technologies across all levels of education. Recent studies show that, the successful implementation of the educational technologies depends largely on the attitudes of the educators. Many research points out that, a teacher’s attitude or belief is one of the several important human factors which has a significant impact on the Techno-

pedagogy and the implementation of the technology in classroom. The attitude of teachers is a major enabling/disabling factor in the adoption of the technology. The teachers with positive attitudes towards the technology feel more comfortable while using it and they usually incorporate it into their teaching activities. The teachers' negative attitudes towards technology changed after training about technology use.

6. Ways to Achieve Techno-Pedagogy

The use of technological facilities in learning environments gained importance in India. So the teachers are supposed to perceive the use of technology as a natural part of their profession in order to be able to conjoin the investments for enhancing the learning of students. The teachers have to integrate information and communication technologies with teaching and learning processes. Besides, the teachers should not only point out how they use ICT at their teaching and learning environments in their lesson plans, but also use these technologies to support the student centered strategies. However, integrating technology into teaching cannot be achieved overnight. Several researchers indicate that the teachers are supposed to overcome some stages.

At first stages, the teachers tend to use the technology almost not at all, however later on; they consider the technology as an instrument which necessities to be taught. As the use of technology increases, they tend to perceive it as an instrument to aid the instruction, rather than being a core educational topic (Hixon & Buckenmeyer, 2009). After the technology usage skills of science teachers have been increased and they managed to integrate the technology with the learning environments. A Techno-pedagogical skill has to be implementing in teacher education program. Also it needs to be taught for the in-service teachers along with professional development program.

7. Conclusion

The best teacher brings diverse experiences and frames of reference to the classroom. In this modern scenario the teacher who uses technology in teaching-learning process plays a vital role. Technology improves learning and makes the teaching-learning process more interesting. So the techno-pedagogical skill of the teachers has in need to be increased and also should bring positive attitude towards techno-pedagogy.

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